

THE ROLE OF CULTURE TOWARDS THE DEVELOPMENT OF MARKET ECONOMY IN QUANG NGAI PROVINCE, VIETNAM

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Abstract:

Culture plays a crucial role in the development of society in general and the economy in particular in Quang Ngai province, Vietnam. Culture is not only the spiritual foundation of society but also the goal and the motivation for economic development. Over the years, culture has assumed its role and has gained certain achievements in the process of economic development. However, there have been still shortcomings that need to be overcome timely. In this article, we boldly propose some basic solutions to deal with above limitations.

Keywords: culture, economy, develop, target, role

1. Introduction

It can be affirmed that culture plays a significant role for human life in general and the economy in particular. The World Organization (UNESCO) states that *“regardless of whatever level of economic development, or whatever political and economic trends, culture and development are two aspects attached to each other. Whenever a country sets itself an economic development goal that separates its cultural environment, it is certain that the economic and cultural imbalances will seriously occur, and its creative potential will greatly slow down”*. The above judgment shows that a developed country needs to associate cultural development with general development, and culture plays an important part in the harmonious development of a country.

2. Content

2.1. The role of culture for the development of market economy in Vietnam today

In the history of human development, many countries in the world have said that if they would like to develop their country, their economy, science and technology need to be developed. After applying this policy for a while, the economies of these countries

have made significant progress. However, it has also led to huge corollaries which are social conflict, moral and cultural decay has been increasing, all of which lead to slow down the economic growth and fall into crisis. Many countries are conscious of the importance of cultural role for the country development in general and the economy in particular, they said that in order to achieve sustainable economic growth, it is necessary to associate economic development with cultural development. So what role does culture play in the current economic development in Quang Ngai Province, Vietnam?

Culture is both the goal and the motivation of the process of developing market economy in Quang Ngai province, Vietnam. *“As a subject, human carries out the development of society, first of all the production force. As an object, human enjoys the fruits of that development. Without human, there is no enjoyment nor dedication - that means no development.”* According to the above judgment, the development must associate with the human and for human. When the cultural level of human resources is constantly enhanced, it will be a significant factor promoting socio-economic development. Culture plays a part in improving intellectuals, skills, expertise, techniques, ethical qualities... etc. However, we must also affirm that the quality of human resources is the product of education process. But human resources only develop properly when combining physical and intellectual factor with cultural factor. Also, we can discuss this issue in current business operation. If we study this issue carefully, it can be seen that business activities in all forms are closely associated with cultural activities. The purpose of business affairs is to meet the needs of human enjoyment. Human needs are more and more stringent and forcing investors to research, explore and stimulate the creativity of members participating in business activities. When manufacturing any products, investors must carefully understand the market, target, district and region, which have become an important culture in production and business. The enhancement of the culture role in production and business will contribute to promoting the growing business as well as avoiding capital degradation.

When mentioning to economic development, if we ignore the role of science and technology, this research is not sufficient. As an inevitable matter, science and technology are one of the vital factors for economic development. So how is the role of culture reflected in the development of science and technology? We know that science is the process of discovering new theories, new knowledge about the natural world, society and human thinking; it is an expression of human cultural creativity. In this role, culture becomes a resource to promote economic development.

In order to better understand the role of culture in the development of market economy in Quang Ngai province; in this section, we will examine its current situation. It can be affirmed that, culture and economy have mutual dialectical relationship, in which culture belongs to the architectural superstructure but culture plays a role as one of the foundations for economic development. Therefore, culture has contributed to creating high quality human resources for the economy nowadays. Culture not only helps people to be more perfect, but also makes contribution to the comprehensive

development of production, gradual improvement of management mechanisms. In addition, it can harmonize the relationships in the production process and consolidate competitive abilities as well as reduce economic inequality towards building model of sustainable economic development.

Since opening the economy, culture has shown its role and contributed significantly to the formation and economic development of Quang Ngai province. The process of opening up the economy has facilitated the development in all aspects, in which culture is not an exception. The multi-dimensional cultural exchange has contributed to make Vietnamese culture in general and Quang Ngai province in particular more and more progressive but still retain our national identity. The continuous progress of culture has been involved significantly in the economic development of Quang Ngai province. Culture has taken a part in enhancing economic activities and improving human resources. It also has a stake in creating good personal qualities for local people in Quang Ngai province such as solidarity, dynamism, creativity, dare to think, dare to do, dare to take responsibility. The culture has also a factor in making Quang Ngai province step by step remove obstacles, create momentum for development to compete with other provinces in the region.

In current socialist-oriented market economy, the role of culture is becoming more and more essential than ever since the development of culture has penetrated deeply into the laborers' minds, which has promoted the quality of labor. Workers have considered that raising their professional level is an indispensable requirement in this era. The human resources in Quang Ngai province are gradually "making changes" to initially abandon the wet rice agriculture habit to enter the market economy. The progress of culture has helped Vietnamese people be highly adaptable to the new situation but still retain the traditional beauty of the noble humanity of Vietnam. Culture has a part in modernizing the economy in the form of gradually reducing physical labor and improving intelligence to promote economic development. Industrial modernization will be the basic and decisive factor for production in order to improve labor productivity and reduce labor intensity to lessen product expenses and prices. Thus, culture plays a part of improving creativity in science and technology. It has not only a role in increasing the economic value of the industry but also promoting the economic restructuring of Quang Ngai province in the trend of pushing up the value of industries utilized by high employment of science and technology.

The role of culture has been expressed in organizing and managing the economy. The process of industrialization - modernization requires each business to organize and manage the economy in accordance with the general trend of the domestic and foreign economy, which avoiding the crisis is an urgent task. The renovation of effective economic management and organization must include culture role since the economy and culture cannot be separated from each other but coexist. The role of culture in organizing and managing economy will contribute to promoting society for sustainable development. And when culture does not play its role, the economy will slow down its development. It is manifested in specific issues such as: *First*, when culture does not

penetrate deeply into human resources, it will lead to poor awareness, not improving skills and professional qualifications. Because of which it greatly affects economic development. In addition, the training in colleges and universities currently focuses in theory but lacks practical activities. Also, the lack of cohesion between schools and employers has caused more and more unemployment. With the thought of desiring to become a teacher has led to paradoxes in the present society such as "*there are too many chiefs but not enough Indians*" or learners do not identify their field of study...etc. Those conflicts have greatly affected the restructuring process and economic development of Quang Ngai province. *Second*, when science and technology do not include the role of culture, in which we still recognize that science and technology - a basic field of culture - have contributed to the increase in economic value and economic restructuring of Quang Ngai province in the right orientation. However, if considering this issue comprehensively, there are still basic limitations such as "keen on low-cost things" or "interests in using outdated things" are ones of the factors that make the science-technology in Quang Ngai province underdeveloped or develop depressively even. The fact that Quang Ngai province in particular and Vietnam in general using technology which is outdated from 20 to 30 years compared to the world is becoming popular, which leads to low labor productivity, high fuel consumption and pushing up the product prices, all of which make products lack their competitiveness in the market. *Third*, the "immunity" of indigenous culture is low compared to the foreign culture. The process of developing socialist-oriented market economy has created the exchange in all aspects including culture. The cultural exchange has initially brought great achievements to build an advanced culture imbued with national identity, which makes the culture contribute significantly to economic development in Quang Ngai province. However, there is still an unwholesome cultural contamination of foreign culture that has made the socio-economy in Quang Ngai province decline considerably. That is the introduction of a cohabitation lifestyle, or pragmatism and selfish lifestyle that trample on the beautiful traditional cultural features of Vietnam; there are evils pursuing the surplus value such as trade of fake goods, knockoffs, banned national goods; or there are some intentional violations of law such as smuggling, cahoots, breaking the state law, circumvention of the state law etc.

Culture is superstructure framework but it can impact on infrastructure in a positive way. However, the above limitations that we have mentioned about culture role in economic development stem from the following issues; *first, the duality of integration process*. We cannot deny that the integration process has brought some advantages in all aspects for Quang Ngai province; on the other hand, it also has some limitations that negatively impact on many fields including culture. That impact has led to the decline in morality, the lifestyle of human resources as well as the polarization between the rich and the poor is increasingly evident in society. Along with that issue, the asynchronous development among districts and regions has made socio-economic development in Quang Ngai province not really harmonious and unsustainable. The process of cultural exchange and acculturation has created conflicts, disruption of many

cultural national values such as the traditional family culture of Quang Ngai province which is gradually fading away; the lifestyle of young people is tending to be pragmatism etc. *Second, there is a massive spontaneous migration of human resources.* This migration process has established cultural exchanges among regions throughout the country but it also caused negative phenomena in the social and cultural life, which is one of the causes that limits the role of culture in socio-economic development in Quang Ngai province. The majority of human resources migrating to industrial parks and cities have been untrained, which has caused considerable concerns to local authorities. This process has also triggered an increase in unemployment situation and social evils more and more. *Third, the subject of cultural awareness is not really homogeneous among regions.* Lack of knowledge and awareness of culture have led to passive and original acquisition of new cultural flows. This acquisition has been a factor in fading the traditional cultural values of the nation. While in the urban areas where the reception and strong impact of cultural flows initially have created the "cultural immunity", in rural and remote areas, the feature of "cultural immunity" which is not distinctive leads to the unwholesome reception of the original cultural flow, which is unavoidable. The disparity in cultural awareness accompanied by the massive migration of human resources from rural to urban areas makes authorities to cope with many difficulties in management and propaganda.

2.2. Several basic measures to promote the culture role in developing market economy in Quang Ngai province

It can be affirmed that the process of integration and culture has shown its role as a factor and objective of the socio-economic development process in Quang Ngai province. However, there are still many shortcomings that make the culture not fully express its role, which becomes the challenge that needs timely resolution. In this section, we boldly suggest the following basic tactics such as:

First, economic development must be associated with cultural development. We need to affirm that culture is a factor of the goal and motivation of economic development; therefore, the association of economic and cultural development is urgent for Quang Ngai province. In order to do this, it is necessary to eliminate the idea that economic development is separated from culture. The cultural enhancement for the sustainable economic development of Quang Ngai province in the integration process needs to fully master the above viewpoints of authorities of Quang Ngai province in particular and the Vietnamese government in general. Besides, there is also a demand for short-term strategies and foresee vision, in which the construction of culture is an essential task in the cause of innovation. The solutions proposed must be close to reality and suitable to the local situation, which are both modern and relevant to Vietnamese people. Culture must be deeply absorbed into people, and it can promote its role in economic development. The association of cultural development with economic development has been proved its exactness by domestic and international science. The interaction between them is an significant factor of development in general, so culture

and economy make the premise for each other to coexist. The Communist Party of Vietnam has affirmed that "*culture is the spiritual foundation of society as well as the goal and motivation for sustainable development of the country. Culture must be placed on par with economy, socio-politics*" (Central Propaganda Department, 2014).

Second, the propagation and education of culture need enhancing further so that culture can penetrate into the subconscious of human resources in order to promote economic development. What making culture embed into people's consciousness requires the authorities to make every effort to propagate and manage cultural education. When people realize the significance of culture for themselves, for their families and society, their practical actions will bring high efficiency. Thus, the agreement between awareness and practice will contribute to promoting economic development. To instill culture into the subconscious of human resources requires the authorities at all levels to carry out some basic tasks such as propaganda, education, persuasion, management etc. In term of cultural propaganda, it can be implemented by many different forms and channels. For education, it is necessary to closely connect families with schools and localities where they reside. For persuasion, it is essential to respect the people and make focused conversation with them. For management, managers need to be skillful, strict and legal.

Third, further improving the cultural management in the integration period is to constantly improve the role of culture for economic development in Quang Ngai province in the current period. It can be said that the current cultural management in Quang Ngai province is facing many difficulties and challenges. In order to overcome the limitations, it is indispensable to get the right orientation and long-term strategies as well as strictly manage the culture. The management of culture in the new period requires a strict and synchronous combination between authorities at all levels. Improving the leading role of the Party and the administration of the government is one of the crucial solutions to contribute to improving the quality of cultural development of the country. Further improvement of cultural management issues will promote the role of culture in economic development in Quang Ngai province. In order to do that, it is substantive to link economic development with cultural development. Cultural management team needs to constantly improve and foster their professional skills. The authorities must regularly inspect, examine, supervise and coordinate with local staffs to improve the leadership capacity of cultural management organizations. The entire management system must constantly be consolidated so that it becomes condensed, effective and righteous. In order to do that it is vital to make a personnel revolution focusing on some criteria such as; the first is talent; second is virtue; the third is patriotism; the fourth is thinking and being able to be innovative, democratic and integrate; the fifth is a dare to think, dare to do, dare to take responsibility as well as further promoting the people's role in the work of cultural management.

3. Conclusion

It can be realized that culture plays an extremely important role for sustainable economic development in Quang Ngai province. Culture has contributed to improving the quality of human resources. Culture has initially asserted its role as a factor to the development of production forces and production relations. However, there are still certain shortcomings that need to be dealt with timely to further link the relationship between economic development and cultural development.

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